

Finding and Reusing Research Data

Finding and reusing research data can be a multi-step process that involves identifying suitable datasets through specialized repositories, metasearch engines, or data journals, and critically evaluating their relevance, quality, and reuse conditions.

Finding research data

Here are some steps to help you find research data:

- Clearly define the research question or topic for which you need data. This will help you identify the specific type of data you require.
- Determine the appropriate sources where you can find research data:
 - **Domain-specific, interdisciplinary or institutional data repositories:** Research data repositories are specialized online platforms where research data can be uploaded and shared together with the related metadata. [Re3data](#) (Registry of Research Data Repositories), which offers many filter options, can be used to find research data repositories.
 - **Metasearch engines specialized in research data:** Metasearch engines enable the simultaneous retrieval of several research data repositories. Be aware that none of the metasearch engines will query all available repositories. Therefore, not all relevant datasets may be found. Examples for metasearch engines are:
 - [b2find.eudat.eu](#)
 - [datacite.org](#) (international, non-profit)
 - [Google Dataset search](#) (especially for open government data)
 - [Mendeley Data](#)
 - [OpenAire](#) (especially data from EU projects)
 - **Data journals:** Check whether there are data journals relevant to your field. Data journals publish articles that describe datasets in detail, but without interpreting them. A list of data journals is provided by [forschungsdaten.org](#).

Reusing research data

If you discover a dataset that might be relevant to your research question, you can use the documentation and metadata provided with the dataset to evaluate the following key considerations:

- Who compiled the data? (assess the reliability of the source)
- How and for what purpose were the data generated?
- Under what conditions were the data generated?
- How is the dataset structured?
- Are the data suitable for answering my research question?
- Do I have access to the data?
- Can and may I combine or enrich the data with other datasets?

Remember to comply with all applicable data usage guidelines, obtain any necessary permissions or licenses, and ensure your use of the data adheres to ethical and legal requirements.

Citation

If you reuse a dataset for a research project, it is important to cite it properly. The citation should include the following information:

- Author
- Title of the dataset
- Year of publication
- Repository
- Version (if indicated)
- Persistent identifier

Persistent identifiers

Persistent identifiers allow scientists and repositories to uniquely identify persons or cite datasets. Here are some examples of widely used persistent identifiers:

- **DOI: Digital Object Identifier**

A unique alphanumeric string assigned by a registration agency (e.g. DataCite, Crossref) to identify content and provide a persistent link to its location on the Internet.

- **ARK ID: Archival Resource Key Identifier**

ARK ID is particularly useful for hierarchically structured data objects.

- **ORCID: Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier**

It provides an identifier for authors as they engage in research, scholarship, and innovation activities. It is highly recommended that you also create an ORCID for yourself.

